

GAS SPECIES IN Al 2014/SiC MMC SPRAY CO-DEPOSITED AND POWDER EXTRUSIONS

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ABSTRACT

Degassing has been frequently proved to be an important step in the P/M processing (extrusion) of aluminium heat treatable alloys and therefore it is thought to play a relevant role in the processing of aluminium matrix composites by P/M. For equivalent MMCs produced by extrusion of spray co-deposited billets it has been claimed that this step can be dispensed with.

In the present work two types of material were produced by hot extrusion (300°C, 16:1) using either a spray co-deposited billet or a canned and degassed powder mixture, both containing SiC particulates in a matrix of an Al 2014 alloy.

Mass spectrometry was used to detect the gas species evolved from the loose powders and from the fractured surfaces of the extruded materials in the solution treated condition. It was found that the temperature spectrum of the gas species evolved from the powder mixture is displaced to higher temperatures (~25°C) when compared with the aluminium powder. The consolidated spray co-deposited material does not release any significant amount of gas species in opposition to the behaviour of the P/M material for which even argon was detected.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of powder degassing on the final properties of totally densified P/M aluminium products seems to be a matter of controversy on the subject of how critical this fabrication step should be considered. Some information is already available about the gas species evolved during the process of heating up aluminium alloy powders (1-5). This gas may of course become entrapped during consolidation affecting the efficiency of this step and get evolved during further heat treatments having a deleterious effect on the mechanical properties (6). The same type of problem will be eventually present on dealing with powder mixtures suitable for the production of aluminium MMCs with the added complication of the mixed powders containing ceramic particulates.

When starting a project on the production and mechanical characterization of totally densified aluminium alloy/SiCp MMC, the authors were however faced with the total absence of information on the degassing characteristics of this type of material. The present paper reports a study on the degassing behaviour of the MMC Al 2014 + 15% SiCp fabricated by powder metallurgy. Mass spectrometry analysis (MSA) was used to identify the gas species evolved from loose powder mixtures in order to better define the degassing temperature of the mixture. An evaluation of the degassing efficiency was also carried out by tensile rupturing, in vacuum, heat treated specimens and MSA of the evolved gas species. A similar program of experiments was performed on a spray co-deposited billet extrusion (Al 2014 + 9.3% SiCp) for which absence of entrapped gas problems has been claimed. The relevance of the information here obtained is discussed in another paper dealing with processing parameters and mechanical properties (7).

EXPERIMENTAL

The MSA tests were carried out under high vacuum (10^{-3} to 10^{-5} Pa) and a quadrupole mass spectrometer Balzers QMG 064 to identify the gaseous species was used.

Table 1 Degassing conditions of loose powders

Material	Median part. size (μm)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time (min.)
Al 2014 (ALCAN)	78	400	110
		390	185
SiC F600 (SIKA)	12	475	130
SiC F800 (ESK)	8	475	155
Al + 15% SiC (SIKA)		400	160

ture surfaces were monitored and recorded with the same mass spectrometer. For comparison, identical tests were also carried out on an extruded spray co-deposited Al 2014 matrix composite with 9.3% SiCp. The specimens were stressed to rupture as solution heat treated for 35 minutes at 502°C .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Loose powder

The effect of temperature on the amount of gaseous species evolving from the powder particles is shown in Figs. 1 and 2 (a); Fig. 2 (b) shows the effect of time at temperature for the silicon carbide (the curves are similar for both types of SiC). From the degassing curves it is notorious the absence of a water vapour peak around 150°C as usually referred in the literature (1-5). It is believed that the usual operation of previously degassing the apparatus could eventually eliminate part of the water of the powder sample; in fact in the only experiment completed without previous degassing (Fig. 1 (a)), a change in slope around 110°C could be observed in the H_2O curve. It is also relevant the amount of H_2O still desorbing at 400°C from all the powders. In the case of the Al alloy powder and mixture the range of temperature could not be extended above 400°C because the presence of volatile elements in the alloy (Zn and Mg) would interfere with a correct interpretation of the curves.

The apparently different behaviour of the Al alloy powder and of the mixture in the range $370 - 400^{\circ}\text{C}$ is also worth noting. The 2014 powder yields, above $\sim 370^{\circ}\text{C}$, a decrease in the water partial pressure coupled with an increase of all the other gaseous species (Fig. 1 (a)). On the other hand there is a general decrease of all species above this temperature when SiC is present, as well as a shift of the peaks from 325 to 350°C (Fig. 1 (b)). The SiC alone shows that within this temperature range there is also a decrease of all desorbing species, forming minima at $\sim 430^{\circ}\text{C}$, i.e. 60°C higher than for the aluminium powder (Fig. 2 (a)). It looks as if the presence of 15% SiC in the mixture more than compensates for the increase in partial pressure of all gaseous species except H_2O evolved from the Al alloy powder, which occurs just below 400°C .

The evolution of CO and CO_2 from Al alloy powders during degassing has also been reported by other authors (1, 2) although no justification for this is yet available. After three hours of isothermal degassing of the Al alloy powder and of the mixture at around 400°C , an appreciable decrease in the H_2O partial pressure has taken place while the H_2 partial pressure only slightly decreases its initial level. A similar experiment carried out with both types of SiC at 475°C discloses however a different

The loose powders were heated up in a quartz reaction tube at a rate of $\sim 3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min.}$ and kept at temperature until the total pressure was constant (Table 1), at which point almost all the gaseous species are supposed to have desorbed from the particles surface.

Previous degassing of the apparatus (except the quartz tube) was carried out at $250 - 300^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 to 20 hours. This apparatus is similar to the one described by Leflour et al (8).

Canned mixtures containing 15% SiCp (SIKA) were degassed at different temperatures for 4 hours and extruded; small notched specimens ($10 \times 10 \times 6 \text{ mm}$) machined from the extruded rods were ruptured using a mini tensile machine inserted in the slightly modified apparatus used to degas the loose powders. The gases released from the rup-

behaviour, the H_2O vapour partial pressure still remaining at a high level after the same time (Fig. 2 (b)).

Fig. 1 Effect of temperature on the degassing of:
a) Al 2014; b) Al 2014 + 15% SiC (SIKA)

Fig. 2 Degassing of SiC (ESK)
a) Effect of temperature; b) gas evolution at 475°C

2. Densified material

The consolidated composites were obtained using two types of raw materials: Al 2014/SiC powder mixtures and a spray co-deposited billet. These materials were extruded using the same process parameters. Based on the results obtained from the degassing experiments carried out with the constituent powders, three degassing temperatures were tried: 350, 400 and 500°C. The highest degassing temperature was tried because the SiC showed an accelerated evolution of gas particularly H_2O above $\sim 450^\circ C$ (Fig. 2) and the T_6 heat treatment of the consolidated material includes a $\sim 500^\circ C$ solution treatment.

Degassing of the canned and tapped powder mixtures was constantly monitored by measuring pressure and temperature. Fig. 3 shows a typical plot obtained during the heating up stage to a 400°C degassing temperature. By comparing this figure with Fig. 1 (b) obtained for the corresponding loose powder, it may be concluded that there is a fair agreement between the two independent types of evidence including, in both cases, a peak at ~350°C.

Fig. 3 Pressure variation in the primary vacuum circuit, during the heating up to 400°C of a canned mixture

The influence of the processing route is easily detected when comparing the gaseous species released from the P/M (Fig. 4) and from the spray co-deposited (Fig. 5 (a)) composites rupture surfaces. The curves drawn in Fig. 4 are typical of the P/M materials showing the release of some amount of H₂ and H₂O, as well as of O₂ and N₂. The argon trapped during the Al 2014 atomization is evolved on rupture due to sudden opening of pores (Fig. 6) in the metal particles. On the contrary, significant amount of gaseous species were evolved from the spray co-deposited material (Fig. 5 (a)).

Fig. 4 Gases detected on rupture of a 2014 + 15% Si material degassed at 400°C; specimen tested in the solution heat treated condition (502°C, 35 min.). Total pressure in chamber ~ 10⁻⁵ Pa

The effect of degassing temperature is clear when comparing Figs. 5 (b) and (c); the amount of gaseous species evolved from the material degassed at 500°C is lower than that evolved from material degassed at 350°C. This evidence can not be directly compared with the curves in Fig. 4 because, in this case, the mass spectrometer chamber total pressure was much lower ($\sim 10^{-5}$ Pa) and therefore much more sensitive.

Fig. 5 Gases detected on rupture of specimens tested in the solution heat treated condition (502°C, 35 min.): a) co-deposited composite Al 2014 + 9.3% SiC; b) Al 2014 + 15% SiC (SIKA), degassed at 350°C; c) Al 2014 + 15% SiC (SIKA) degassed at 500°C. Total pressure in the chamber $\sim 10^{-3}$ Pa

Fig. 6 Pore in Al powder particle

CONCLUSIONS

For the materials used in this work, the following behaviour was obtained:

1. Al 2014/15% SiCp powder mixtures show a peak of gas evolution at about 350°C which is ~ 25°C higher than for the metal powder alone.
2. For the composite powder mixture there is an effective increase in degassing power as the temperature is increased up to 500°C, in particular in what concerns the removal of H₂.
3. The spray co-deposited Al 2014/SiCp composite does not show any significant gas evolution on rupture of the consolidated material.

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REFERENCES

1. J.T. Morgan et al., Proceedings of AIME Symposium on High Strength Powder Metallurgy Al Alloys, Dallas, Texas, 17 - 18 Feb. 1982, 193 - 206.
2. Young-Won Kim et al., Journal of Metals, August 1985, 27 - 33.
3. J.C. Leflour, E. Andrieu, Y. Bienvenu, Horizons of Powder Metallurgy Part I, Proceedings of the 1986 Int. Powder Met. Conference, W.A. Kaysser and W.J. Huppmann, EPMPF, 1986, 759 - 762.
4. M.J. Couper et al., Proceedings of the International Conference on PM Aerospace Materials, Luzern, 2-4 Nov. 1987, MPR Publishing Services, 28.
5. H. Schlich et al., *ibid*, 31.
6. M.H. Carvalho, H. Carvalhinhos and C.M. Sellars, "Extrusion and properties of 7075 ingot and particulate", submitted to Powder Metallurgy.
7. M.H. Carvalho et al., "Effect of degassing conditions and SiC type of a P/M 2014 MMC" VII International Conference on Composite Materials, Beijing, China, 1 - 4 August 1989.
8. J.C. Leflour, E. Andrieu, Y. Bienvenu, Conf. on Advanced Investigation Methods, Saint-Etienne, France, 19 - 20 Nov. 1986.